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Terms and abbreviations

BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DM	Dissemination Manager
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
ETIP- SNET	European Technology & Innovation Platforms - Smart Networks for Energy Transition
GA	Grant Agreement
GAM	General Assembly Meeting
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
NGIoT	Next Generation Internet of Things
PM	Project Manager
PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
RE	Restricted
SC	Steering Committee
SGAM	Smart Grid Reference Architecture Model
TM	Technical Manager
WP	Work package
WPL	Work package Leader

Executive Summary

This document summarises the networking activities performed in PLATOON to seek synergies and ensure cooperation with other related H2020 funded projects, in particular with those which are represented at the BRIDGE initiative as well as with other cooperation groups such as ETIP-SNET, NGIOT and OPENDEI. Also, it specifically covers the one to one collaboration with other two similar projects which are part of OPENDEI, namely INTERCONNECT and PLATONE projects. Besides, this document also summarises the main networking activities performed under the umbrella of different industrial groups and clusters such as International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), Big Data Value Association (BDVA), GAIA-X and European Industry Clusters. Finally, the document collates the marketing strategy and activities developed to create the PLATOON Community.

1 Introduction

This document summarises the different networking activities performed in PLATOON to seek synergies and ensure cooperation with other related H2020 funded projects. Section 2 of the document covers the different collaborations with in particular with those which are represented at the BRIDGE initiative as well as with other related H2020 funded projects through different cooperation groups such as BRIDGE, ETIP-SNET, NGIOT and OPENDEI. Also, it specifically covers the one to one collaboration with other two similar projects which are part of OPENDEI, namely INTERCONNECT and PLATONE projects. Section 3 covers the main networking activities performed under the umbrella of different industrial groups and clusters such as International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), Big Data Value Association (BDVA), GAIA-X and European Industry Clusters. Finally, section 4 collates the marketing strategy and activities developed to create the PLATOON Community.

2 Networking Activities through Cooperation Groups

2.1 BRIDGE

PLATOON actively cooperates with other H2020 projects through the BRIDGE cooperation group. BRIDGE is a European Commission initiative which unites Horizon 2020 Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands, and Digitalisation Projects to create a structured view of cross-cutting issues which are encountered in the demonstration projects and may constitute an obstacle to innovation¹.

PLATOON actively participates in the BRIDGE General Assemblies and regularly provides feedback on develop questionnaires in order to unite the challenges and developments from the different projects.

In addition, PLATOON is actively involved in the Data Management working group and the Replicability & Scalability Task Force.

The Data Management working group is focused on the same pillars as PLATOON, namely, Interoperability, Data Governance/Trust and Data Analytics, covering the following aspects:

- Communication Infrastructure, embracing the technical and non-technical aspects of the communication infrastructure needed to exchange data and the related requirements, including issues faced by TSO and DSO.
- Cybersecurity and Data Privacy, entailing data integrity, customer privacy and protection.
- Data Handling, including the framework for data exchange and related roles and responsibilities, together with the technical issues supporting the exchange of data in a secure and interoperable manner, and the data analytics techniques for data processing.

¹ <https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/>

Recently, the BRIDGE Data Management working group has published an architecture for Data Exchange which summarises the different initiatives, associations, processes, etc. covering the main angles defined in the SGAM ²(Smart Grid Reference Architecture Model), namely. business, function, information, communication and component. The figure below shows the mapping of the PLATOON project against the reference architecture for Data Exchange of BRIDGE where the red boxes define the aspects of the BRIDGE architecture covered in PLATOON.

Figure 1: PLATOON mapping architecture for Data Exchange of BRIDGE

2.2 ETIP-SNET

PLATOON actively cooperates with other related H2020 through the ETIP SNET ³cooperation group. European Technology & Innovation Platforms (ETIPs) have been created by the European Commission in the framework of the new Integrated Roadmap Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan) by bringing together a multitude of stakeholders and experts from the energy sector. The ETIP Smart Networks for Energy Transition (SNET) role is to guide Research, Development & Innovation (RD&I) to support Europe’s energy transition.

PLATOON has participated in several workshops organized by ETIP-SNET where different aspects regarding the energy transition and digitalisation have been discussed along with other H2020 projects. For instance, on the 21st April 2021, PLATOON participated in the 11th ETIP SNET Regional Workshop: briefing session 3 as a panellist where the different challenges around digitalisation of smart grids were discussed with an special focus on data security, privacy and sovereignty and its relationship with the so-called data spaces.

² https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/xpert_group1_reference_architecture.pdf

³ <https://www.etip-snet.eu/>

Moreover, PLATOON also contributes with ETIP-SNET by regularly providing feedback on questionnaires in order to unite the challenges and developments from the different H2020 projects.

2.3 NGIOT

The Next Generation Internet of Things (NGIoT) initiative is a growing community of projects and related initiatives at work to maximise the power of IoT made in Europe. NGIoT works to lower the barrier for adoption and development of IoT-empowered solutions, by supporting business models, innovation and skills.

In a “network of network” ecosystem, NGIoT consists of ongoing projects and upcoming funding opportunities at work for a human-centric and sustainable digital transition. NGIoT projects are working to achieve H2020 goals while Horizon Europe will bring new opportunities to launch research and innovation projects across Europe and beyond. NGIoT works in close collaboration with related technology networks including cloud, Edge, Artificial Intelligence, 5G telecommunications networks and services, cybersecurity and blockchain.

PLATOON actively collaborates with NGIOT by taking part of events (webinars, workshops...). For instance, on 18th May 2021, PLATOON participated in a dedicated workshop around IoT and Edge Computing for the energy domain where we presented the approach followed in PLATOON and gave some insights on the Edge-Cloud framework that we are building as part of the project. The workshop also served to share views and lessons learnt with the European Commission and relevant associations, networks, and projects.

2.4 OPENDEI

PLATOON actively cooperates with other related H2020 through the OPENDEI cooperation group. OPEN DEI focuses on “Platforms and Pilots” to support the implementation of next generation digital platforms in four basic industrial domains: Manufacturing, Agriculture, Energy and Healthcare. PLATOON actively participates in the Energy domain.

In fact, PLATOON is leading the Working Group 3 “Linking Ecosystems” where they held regular meetings with other projects from OPEN DEI to plan, define and promote joint communication and dissemination activities. In this sense, PLATOON together with OPEN DEI is planning a joint event to be held in Bilbao on the 23rd September around Data Spaces in the Energy Sector. In this event relevant institutions (IDSA, BDVA, GAIA-X), relevant energy and ICT company and representatives from other projects from OPEN DEI will meet together to discuss around the hot topic of data spaces specifically for the energy sector. In this forum different aspects around data security, privacy and sovereignty will be discussed. This event will be a perfect opportunity to establish again physical networking activities in a new challenging post COVID-19 era.

Furthermore, PLATOON is also actively involved in the Data Management Task Force (TF1). This Task Force lead by IDSA brings together experts from four domains and various data spaces initiatives to collaborate and define the design principles for data spaces

implementation in a unified way. Recently, this working group has published a position paper on “Design Principles for Data Spaces”⁴ where PLATOON has actively contributed together with other H2020 projects.

Moreover, PLATOON regularly participates in events and workshops organized by OPENDEI. For instance, on 19th May 2021 PLATOON participated in the OPEN-DEI - IdeasForum event where it was discussed together with other H2020 projects the different approaches implemented in the different projects for data exchange and the main challenges and lessons learnt were shared.

2.5 One to One Collaboration with Specific projects

Apart from the joint collaboration through the abovementioned european cooperation groups, PLATOON has also engaged in one to one collaboration with specific projects in the area of digitalisation of smart grids, namely, with InterConnect and PLATONE projects.

2.5.1 InterConnect

InterConnect⁵ is H2020 project funded under the call “DT-ICT-10-2018-19 - Interoperable and smart homes and grids”. The project gathers 50 European entities to develop and demonstrate advanced solutions for connecting and converging digital homes and buildings with the electricity sector by including digital technologies (Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Cloud and Big Data) based on open standards, such as SAREF. InterConnect guarantees the interoperability between equipment, systems and privacy/cybersecurity of user data. The developed solutions are implemented and validated in large-scale test-sites in Portugal, Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, Italy, Greece and France.

The main objectives of the project are the following:

- Marketplace of integrated digital platforms bridging the gap between IoT and energy
- Establish interoperability framework validating SAREF and semantic interoperability
- User centric energy and non-energy services

One of the aspects of the two initiatives – projects, PLATOON / INTERCONNECT, that constitute a convergence zone is of course located at the level of interfaces and interoperability models. These two elements seek in the respective projects to respond to the challenges of their respective cases of use related to the different pilots and to provide means and tools to allow these interoperable flows of data and values that can be manipulated by dedicated services that rely heavily on digital technologies. The stake of this collaboration could be built in two main axes, namely the alignment of different information flows (which would respect the constraints of ownership and privacy) by connecting these flows through the ontological model SAREF, which is strongly mobilized in the INTERCONNECT project, and also considered in the USE CASE of the PLATOON project. The identification of a simple case of use between the two projects could be an empirical transposition of this willingness to collaborate. It could also jointly demonstrate the relevance of the postulates and approaches considered within the framework of the European Commission's strategy and projects aimed at promoting the exchange of data and services in the energy field at the European level between several stakeholders.

⁴ <https://design-principles-for-data-spaces.org/>

⁵ <https://interconnectproject.eu/>

Different meetings have been and are being held between PLATOON and INTERCONNECT to define a collaboration roadmap with clear objectives and milestones.

2.5.2 PLATONE

PLATONE ⁶(PLATform for Operation of distribution Networks) is a H2020 funded project corresponding to the call LC-SC3-ES-1-2019 - Flexibility and retail market options for the distribution grid. PLATONE aims at defining new approaches to increase the observability of renewable energy resources and of the less predictable loads while exploiting their flexibility. The consortium of 12 partners from Belgium, Germany, Greece and Italy develop advanced management platforms to unlock grid flexibility and to realize an open and non-discriminatory market, linking users, aggregators and operators. The solutions developed in the project will be tested in three European field trials.

PLATONE and PLATOON could collaborate to demonstrate the interoperability between both projects being able to exchange data and services with each other. In order to demonstrate it the use case in the City of Rome could be used that is part of both projects. In this use case, the PLATONE project could provide the necessary data from some stakeholders that are not part of PLATOON (e.g. Aretti) and PLATOON could provide the data analytics tools to extract value from that data. Furthermore, when it comes to data exchange the complementarity of the proposed approaches (PLATONE – DLT and PLATOON –IDS) could be analysed and accordingly integrated. In conclusion, this collaboration could demonstrate a cross-project ecosystem that will set the basis towards a common European Energy Data Space.

Different meetings have been and are being held between PLATOON and PLATONE to define a collaboration roadmap with clear objectives and milestones.

⁶ <https://www.platone-h2020.eu/>

3 Networking Activities through Industrial groups and Clusters

3.1 International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)

The International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) is a coalition of more than 130 member companies that share a vision of a world where all companies self-determine usage rules and realize the full value of their data in secure, trusted, equal partnerships; and we are making that vision a reality. The goal of this association is to define global standard for international data spaces (IDS) and interfaces, as well as fostering the related technologies and business models that will drive the data economy of the future across industries.

PLATOON actively collaborates with IDSA through different workstreams such as Technical Plugfest and Acceleration programme.

In addition, PLATOON actively participates in the events (webinars, workshops...) organized by IDSA. For instance, PLATOON has participated in the IDSA SUMMIT - ENERGY STREAM celebrated on 22nd June 2021 where notable Energy data spaces successes were showcased to demonstrate their benefits, and gain insights from insiders and users. Among different projects were Basque Offshore Wind Energy Data Space, BD4ENERGY, German EnDaSpace (Fh IEE), Atos Germany Energy Data Space and Dutch Energy case.

In addition, IDSA has helped to disseminate the PLATOON Open Calls and other projects through their network and specifically through Thorsten Huelsmann CFO of IDSA and PLATOON ambassador.

3.2 BDVA – Energy Task Force

Big Data Value Association (BDVA⁷) is an industry-driven international not-for-profit organisation with more than 200 members all over Europe and a well-balanced composition of large, small, and medium-sized industries as well as research and user organizations. BDVA is the private counterpart to the EU Commission to implement the Big Data Value PPP program. BDVA and the Big Data Value PPP pursue a common shared vision of positioning Europe as the world leader in the creation of Big Data Value.

The mission of the BDVA is to develop the Innovation Ecosystem that will enable the data and AI-driven digital transformation in Europe delivering maximum economic and societal benefit, and, achieving and sustaining Europe's leadership on Big Data Value creation and Artificial Intelligence.

PLATOON has recently launched a brand new task force for Energy ⁸within BDVA. The objective of this task force is to create a common understanding between members of the BDVA interested in Big Data and Artificial Intelligence applications applied to the Energy domain.

⁷ <https://www.bdva.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.bdva.eu/task-force-7>

Firstly, given the launch of the GREEN DEAL Programme and its strong dimension in the field of energy, in particular with Cluster 5 - Horizon Europe - Cluster 5: Climate, Energy and Mobility, it is imperative to align this Task Force initiative with the important ambitions of this European initiative.

Secondly, an advanced collaboration on Big Data dimensions between existing projects financed by the European Commission and present within OPEN DEI (INTERCONNECT, INTERFFACE, SYNERGY, BD4OPEN, PLATONE, PLATOON, Coordinet), BRIDGE and other cooperation groups.

3.3 GAIA-X

GAIA-X is a project initiated by Europe for Europe and beyond. Its aim is to develop common requirements for a European data infrastructure, a secure, federated system that meets the highest standards of digital sovereignty while promoting innovation. This project is the cradle of an open, transparent digital ecosystem, where data and services can be made available, collated and shared in an environment of trust. Therefore openness, transparency and the ability to connect to other European countries are central to GAIA-X. Representatives from several European countries and further international partners are currently involved in the project.

In this sense, PLATOON very actively collaborates with GAIA-X by embracing the design principles of the GAIA-X reference architecture and participating in relevant networking events to share vision and lessons learnt with other similar projects. For instance, PLATOON participated in GAIA-X French Hub Presentation in September 2020 and in the DATAWEEK - EUH4D Track Data- 4Energy session on 27th May 2021 where we shared our approach for an End to End Interoperable Ecosystem for Energy Value Chain.

3.4 EUROPEAN CLUSTERS

PLATOON through the Basque Energy Cluster actively collaborates in the network of European Clusters by sharing the vision, progress and lessons learnt from the project with other Clusters at European level.

For instance, the Basque Energy Cluster participated as Keynote speaker in the “Renewable energy” breakout session of the European Cluster Conference 2020, that took place on 10-11th November in a virtual format where presented the PLATOON project and its significant impact in strengthening the competitiveness of the energy value chains.

4 PLATOON Community

This section summarises the marketing strategy and activities developed to create the PLATOON Community.

4.1 PLATOON Community Portal

PLATOON COMMUNITY, was built using the FundingBox community platform. This is a **dynamic and interactive** web-based platform that includes communication services fostering collaborative work, aiming at facilitating interaction among stakeholders and providing information on best practices, trends in the market, etc. The FundingBox platform largely evolved over the time, thanks to users' feedback and new features have been implemented in order to offer an ideal tool to **build up communities around projects and initiatives**.

Figure 2: PLATOON Community Portal

The PLATOON project consortium designed the PLATOON COMMUNITY with an inclusive perspective promoting the inclusion not only of the PLATOON related activities and results but acting also as a gathering **for all those stakeholders interested in the digitisation of the energy sector**. Therefore, the PLATOON community has a wider ambition and perspective than just being the community of the PLATOON project, aiming to become the community of reference in Europe for anyone working or wanting to know more information about the digitisation of the energy sector.

PLATOON Community is benefitting from the FundingBox experience in building communities for several other European projects such as the I-ENERGY, I4MS, INTERCONNECT community and more, with the objective of **transforming** what usually are **static unidirectional websites in a dynamic multidirectional community**, where connections are made and where conversations and knowledge can be gathered and shared.

This communication channel aims to create a real-time community where its participants will be able to easily access a repository of knowledge and finding long-term business opportunities.

4.2 Community Portal in Numbers

We follow up the impact of communication actions in community building, to watch for the project to reach its Key Performance Indicators in terms of dissemination and also to search for potential improvements and implement corrective actions if needed.

Metrics using platform analytics tools that will contribute to measure the attractiveness and dynamics of the community platform are:

- Number of users (sign-ups, new members)
- Numbers of messages (content) posted in the certain period (posts, announcements, files, articles)
- Number of reactions to the content in the certain period
- Number of comments to the content in the certain period
- Other engagement metrics of the community, like percentage of visits during the last 30 days.

To date we have the following statistics:

Table 1: Community in numbers updated to May 20, 2021.

Members	114
Interacting users	135
Messages	82
Replies/Comments	49
Reactions	38

Based on the Figure below, there appears to have been a surge during the Open Call launch in January, which closed beginning of March 2021.

Key Charts

Figure 3: Community in numbers updated to May 20, 2021

4.3 Community growth

PLATOON uses a method called Growth hacking — “a process of rapid experimentation across marketing channels and product development to identify the most efficient ways to grow a

business.⁹”.

With this technique we make the most of both conventional and unconventional marketing experiments to expand a community. The main goal of growth hacking is rapid growth at an early stage by increasing the conversion rate and lowering the cost per customer acquisition, although the customer retention is a key point of any successful growth hacking strategy.

Tactics that are used in Growth Hacking are: search engine optimization, website analytics, content marketing, email campaigns, viral strategies and A/B testing. But it can also involve online community management and social media outreach, both through organic content and paid ads, and influencer marketing.

In coordination with TIB, FBA has developed a PLATOON Communication toolkit, shared with partners, Supportive Partners and Ambassadors in order to be affective in growing the community as well as attracting potential applicants to PLATOON’s Open Calls.

4.4 Growth Hacking Strategy

PLATOON used the following growth hacking strategy which follows a funnel as described below:

- **Acquisition.** The main goal is to lower the acquisition cost of users, and for that a growth hacker has to answer the question ‘How does your target find you?’, to focus the brand awareness strategy on the platforms the target audience is (which social media networks, blogs and online magazines, which online communities and groups, etc.). To date, we have used multiple avenues to reach out to our audience, from our AdWords campaign to attract applicants to the 1st Open Call to regular posts on our social media accounts, offline events such as those described above and blog posts/press releases on our partner’s networks and communication tools.
- **Activation.** Once the target has been acquired, it has to be activated, which means the key performance indicator of this step of the growth hacking funnel is the conversion rate. For that, it is important to answer the question ‘Does your target have a great first experience?’, which in the case of the PLATOON online community would mean ‘Do they join the community?’. We have namely used call to actions to convert the visitors and increase the possibilities for them to join the community. We have publicised the community in FBA’s newsletter that is sent to FBA’s wider ecosystem. We also used the PLATOON helpdesk as a call to action to invite members to join the community.
- **Retention.** Retention focuses its efforts on creating active users or members of a community on a daily, weekly or monthly basis by offering some added value to enlighten them. In the case of a customer, the objective would be that they buy again and again, but in this one, that they become active members. The question that summarises the retention would be ‘Does your target come back?’ We focused on

⁹ Paramount MD, 2020

retaining our community members by providing relevant content such as the following:

- Funding opportunities.
 - Webinars, Q&A sessions from leading organizations, curators and influencers - digital transformation evangelizers that will provide us with exclusive content through cross-promotion partnerships. For that, we will identify the new members joining the community and create tags for them on Spaces to reach out to them and propose them to create content in exchange for promotion within our network. We have done the same with external agents, such as influencers.
 - PLATOON success stories for those selected projects via the Open Call.
 - Helpdesk.
 - Policy news.
- **Referral.** Last, but not least, we expect users, members or customers to spread the word and tell others to help the user base grow organically, although there are also some techniques to encourage them to do it.

4.5 Supportive Partners Programme

The Supportive Partners Programme for communities involves entities from across Europe, such as start-up communities, accelerators, governments, programmes and more to help PLATOON to empower innovation and entrepreneurship in the crossroads of ICT and energy and connect the ecosystem. The “supportive partners” are stakeholders interested in disseminating the project in a win-win cooperation mode. These are identified via community mapping, starting from the PLATOON partners’ networks.

For this purpose, each partner was asked by FBA to identify these entities and to reach out via an email template provided by FBA to send to their respective contacts. Following a response from the supportive partners expressing interest in the role, FBA reached out to each to on-board the confirmed supportive partners. To date, FBA has contacted 15 supportive partners, as a result of the outreach activity run by several of PLATOON partners.

These collaborating entities have been encouraged to share content for dissemination so that the community as a whole would benefit from channelling all information into one place. Content can include, for example:

- Success stories about the implementation of the pilot.
- Recent breakthrough and advances benefiting and business news in this domain,
- Opportunities for SMEs: calls, events, competitions, etc.

For example, [BERRIUP](#) is one of the Supportive Partners who publicised the Open Call in their newsletter as shown in the figure below:

mas importantes en educación de España

empresariales de base tecnológica

Beseif, la forma segura de comprar por Wallapop

Entrevista a Unai Tapia y Sergio Gallastegui, de **Codecontract**

Convocatorias abiertas

INCIBE: programa de Aceleración Internacional para StartUps en Ciberseguridad [SABER MÁS](#)

PLATOON: 1st PLATOON Open Call [SABER MÁS](#)

REACH INCUBATOR: programa de incubación para empresas de Big Data [SABER MÁS](#)

¿Buscas un espacio en el que trabajar y emprender?

[Reserva tu espacio](#)

Figure 4: BERRIUP - 1st PLATOON Open Call publication

A post on LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook was also made by Supportive Partner **vestbee** (hosts CEE Startup & Scaleup Challenges). The Twitter post is included below.

Figure 5: vestbee - 1st PLATOON Open Call publication

Another example is included further below in Section 4.7.

4.6 Ambassador Programme

Ambassadors are responsible for contributing towards the PLATOON community, the PLATOON website, newsletter and our social media channels, engaging with other members. PLATOON is engaging 3 Ambassadors to advocate about the project, with a one year contract from _____ commencing _____ mid-May.

This Ambassador programme will enable us to boost the community growth, focusing in a range of consolidated figures in the domain involved in the project to create awareness through their digital channels, as well as in physical events. They will be participating in PLATOON online Community at FundingBox' Spaces, providing knowledge, expertise and valuable content

The Ambassadors selected for this project are:

1. Nathalie Mitton, **Inria**
2. Jad Nassar, **Yncréa**
3. Thorsten Huelsmann, **International Data Spaces**

Their role in the project is to:

- a. PLATOON's community (on-line community of stakeholders, users and service providers), administered by FBOX PLATOON Community by:
 - posting content on PLATOON community (third parties, news or events) at least once a month.
 - posting in Social Media at least once per month with PLATOON tagging (even reusing PLATOON content reposted from LinkedIn and/or Twitter).
 - Interacting with users.
- b. Organise at least 1 webinar or Q&A session in a form of one-hour public online events. Topics to be covered will be agreed between the Ambassador and FBA.
- c. Providing 4 articles (one per trimester) with length not shorter than 800 words with at least 5 references to external content. Articles shall uniquely refer to the digitalisation of the energy sector with the adoption of data analytics, edge computing, AI & IDS technologies. The articles should also include the Ambassador's bio (brief) at the end. Topics and deadlines will be agreed between the Ambassador and FBA.
- d. Provide informal feedback to FBA on potential influencers who would be of value to the PLATOON Community as well as trends and "hot topics" which could be of interest to the PLATOON Community.

An example of related content by one of PLATOON's Ambassadors can be found on the PLATOON Community [here](#).

4.7 1st Open Call Dissemination

The 1st PLATOON Open Call was disseminated in a number of ways. We primarily utilised our networks and worked with TIB (the communication and dissemination partner) in

disseminating across our PLATOON’s social media channels. We also ran a social media campaign to complement the efforts of the PLATOON Consortium. All material was shared for re-posting by other members of the consortium.

Open Call Announcements on Funding Box PLATOON Community

We made several announcements on the PLATOON community on Fundingbox’s platform which can be seen [here](#) and we also addressed multiple Questions and Answers in our Community Space [here](#).

Social Media Campaign

A social media campaign was run for the two months the Open Call was open.

Figure 6: PLATOON Open Call Dissemination Campaign Overview

Blog Posts:

- [1st PLATOON Open Call open from 4th January to 4th March 2021](#)
- [PLATOON Open Call Q&A Session](#)
- [96 Applications successfully submitted for the PLATOON Open Call](#)

Press Releases

Press releases related to the Open Call Launch were written in English, German, Italian and Spanish and can be found [here](#).

Tweets:

- [Our 1st PLATOON Open Call launched](#)
- [PLATOON is looking for SMEs for our Open Call!](#)
- [Apply for Open Call & enter its Support Programme](#)
- [Up to €150k per project available!](#)
- [To the SMEs from the Energy Sector](#)
- [Discover the very 1st PLATOON Open Call](#)
- [SMEs for Open Call](#)
- [Apply for our Open Call](#)
- [2 weeks to go](#)

Last week, last chance

PLATOON Open Call Q&A Session

96 Applications submitted for the PLATOON Open Call

LinkedIn Posts:

Our 1st PLATOON Open Call launched

PLATOON is looking for SMEs for our Open Call!

Apply for Open Call & enter its Support Programme

Up to €150k per project available!

To the SMEs from the Energy Sector

Discover the very 1st PLATOON Open Call

SMEs for Open Call

Apply for our Open Call

2 weeks to go

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PLATOON Open Call Q&A Session

96 Applications submitted for the PLATOON Open Cal

These posts were disseminated by partners across the **partners networks** e.g. the dissemination through OPEN DEI initiative and its Working Group 3 (WG3) on Linking Ecosystems by the Basque Energy Cluster.

- PLATOON Open Call dissemination material delivered to OPEN DEI and published on their “Open Calls” site : <https://www.opendei.eu/open-calls/>
- Presentation of the Open Call by José Ignacio Hormaeche (WG3 chair on behalf of PLATOON) in the OPEN DEI WG3 follow-up meeting held on Jan, 15th
- PLATOON Open Call dissemination material delivered upon request to representatives of H2020 projects INTERCONNECT and INTERRFACE (also involved in OPEN DEI WG3) so as to be circulated among their respective partners.

Supportive partners were also engaged to disseminate the Open Calls. For example **Tenerdis** — a regional Energy Cluster in France, published about the Open Call in their newsletter. See image below.

APPEL A PROJET EUROPÉEN

PLATOON : Projet européen sur la digitalisation dans le secteur de l'énergie avec « cascade funding » au bénéfice des PME

L'objectif du projet européen Platoon coordonné par Engie est d'améliorer l'excellence opérationnelle dans le secteur de l'énergie via les technologies numériques.

PLATOON veut contribuer à une augmentation de la part des énergies renouvelables, à l'intelligence des réseaux énergétiques, à l'amélioration de l'efficacité énergétique et à l'optimisation de la gestion des actifs énergétiques.

DATE LIMITE DE DÉPÔT : 04/03/2021

CONSULTER →

Figure 7: Tenerrdis - 1st PLATOON Open Call dissemination in their newsletter

The PLATOON Consortium also widely disseminated the Open Call through two webinars.

An online info day organised by the Basque Energy Cluster together with Tecnalía was held on January 27th to disseminate the Open Call among the Basque companies (mainly SMEs & start-ups) attended by representatives from 21 entities

- Announcement on CEPV Twitter account: https://twitter.com/Cluster_Energia/status/1349335948979539973
- Invitation emailing to Basque Energy Cluster member companies and to the Basque network of Business Innovation Centres (business incubators)
- Presentations by José Ignacio Hormaeche (CEPV Managing Director) and Erik Maqueda (PLATOON Tech. Coordinator; Tecnalía) at the event, explaining the basics of the project and the procedure and technical scope for the 1st Open Call.
- Questions & Answers session with the audience after the presentations
- Post on the event published on CEPV website:
 - English: <http://www.clusterenergia.com/innovation/cluster-energia-y-tecnalia-presentan-convocatoria-abierta-proyecto-h2020-platoon-a-un-conjunto-pymes-y-start-ups-vascas-3>
 - Spanish: <http://www.clusterenergia.com/innovacion/cluster-energia-y-tecnalia-presentan-1-convocatoria-abierta-proyecto-h2020-platoon-a-un-conjunto-pymes-y-start-ups-vascas>

Finally, FBA also organised a Q&A webinar held on March 10, 2021 to answer questions from potential applicants as can be shown [here](#).

5 Discussion and conclusion

As per summarised in the document it can be concluded that so far PLATOON project has actively worked on several networking activities and successfully established several synergies and cooperation's with other related H2020 funded projects.

On the one hand, it has actively collaborated through BRIDGE initiative as well as with other cooperation groups such as ETIP-SNET, NGIOT and OPENDEI. In this sense, it is worth highlighting the leading role of PLATOON in OPENDEI Linking Ecosystems Work Steam and the one to one collaboration with other two similar projects which are part of OPENDEI, namely INTERCONNECT and PLATONE projects.

On the other hand, PLATOON has actively collaborated with different industrial groups and clusters such as International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), Big Data Value Association (BDVA), GAIA-X and European Industry Clusters. In this sense it is important to say the critical role played by PLATOON on establishing a brand new Energy Task Force in BDVA.

Besides, regarding the PLATOON Community, it can be concluded that the defined growth hacking strategy and 1st Open Call Dissemination campaign have proven to be effective as it is reflected in the metrics.

Finally, it is worth saying that the PLATOON networking activities is regarded as a continuous important task for the project and thus PLATOON will keep actively working on these activities until the end of the project and beyond. In this sense, in the end of the project (M36) an updated report will be delivered with the updated networking activities.